
THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article, the use of modern technologies in teaching foreign languages offers many opportunities to make teaching more interesting and more effective in terms of improvement. In addition, this modern technological tool attracts students based on their interests ideas are included to help you learn and do.

Key words: Internet, audio and video systems, multimedia, educational computer programs, information technologies, higher education, countries, foreign language teaching, modern technologies.

Modern conditions require not only the use of new technologies in teaching foreign languages, but also changes in teaching methods and the introduction of the latest innovative technologies from the teacher in the process of learning foreign languages. Higher educational institutions prefer to use active teaching methods aimed at forming students' independence, flexibility, and critical thinking. Innovative technologies are the most powerful source of knowledge activities that develop students' creative abilities, interests, skills, and other mental characteristics.

Innovative educational technologies are, first of all, information and communication technologies that are closely related to computerized education. The main problems of using innovative technologies are the composition of computer training programs, their content, and acceptable Web environment regulation.

The Internet can provide invaluable assistance to students in learning a foreign language. The global web provides students with a unique opportunity to use original texts, communicate with native speakers, create a natural language environment, and build cross-cultural collaboration skills. Access to the Internet promotes fluency in a foreign language. The Internet as a means of information transfer is especially relevant for the independent work of students after class. Students are independent while surfing the Internet acquire knowledge, work with large amounts of data, analyze data, and see and solve problems.

Relevance of the topic:

New information technologies such as the Internet, audio and video systems, and multimedia educational computer programs are widely used in higher education

institutions. All these technologies help to create additional opportunities for the development of students' creativity, increase their curiosity, and increase their interest in research work.

In addition, it allows us to effectively solve several didactic tasks:

Improving the ability to read (Reading);

Expand vocabulary with modern foreign words;

Improving monologue and dialogic speech skills;

Discuss Web Internet materials;

With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which is one of the unique features of our time, special attention is being paid to using its possibilities, to fully approach the educational process and to organize it. The 21st century is the age of high technologies, and our modern youth are taking steps not only under the spirit of the time but also by the progress in the electronic world. For this reason, a different approach to the process of teaching the young generation is required. The role of the teacher in the lessons is also changing. The teacher now acts mainly as a guide.

It is time for teachers who aim to keep pace with the times to be ready to enliven any part of the lesson through ICT.

In the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" "Introduction of advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies" by way of teaching the growing young generation to foreign languages, fundamentally improving the system of training specialists who can speak these languages fluently, and based on this, their achievements in world development and wide use of world information resources, international cooperation and communication "creating conditions and opportunities for their development" and the need to implement several important tasks for this. later, teaching using ICT tools was determined as the main subject of education. By this important decision, today, in particular, foreign language lessons were looked at more deeply. To protect the country's honor on the world stage, our youth must first be able to compete with their foreign peers. conducted in English, the international business language.

The role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, in the purposeful organization of game-based lessons that are interesting to students, is very large. is becoming an integral part of the educational process. To teach young people English through a computer, first of all, the teacher himself must be able to use computer technologies at a professional level. it also includes the ability to organize new educational programs based on it. To become a pedagogue of this level, every foreign

language teacher needs to work more on himself in the field of modern technologies. Computer-assisted English language teaching has several advantages over traditional teaching methods. First of all, computer-based English language learners have four areas of language skills (speaking, listening, writing, and reading). will be an opportunity to test their skills. Currently, this is possible with the help of advanced programs. It is only necessary to be able to properly direct the student to this method of education.

In addition, it has been proven that every rule, every word, every concept unit taught in the teaching of foreign languages with the help of a computer is better stored in the student's memory. the ability to deliver in the form of video makes teaching foreign languages through the computer one of the most effective methods. That's why we want to use the rich possibilities of the computer to teach the English language to the students of the 5th grade. It is appropriate to use Word and PowerPoint programs to explain current topics. If the topic is explained using the table views through the Word program, the students will understand it much easier. In PowerPoint, students can be more attracted to the topic by showing these topics in audio, picture, and video formats.

Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in schools. It is known that the lesson is conducted based on various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, have self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a teaching method. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest and strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupils through them. The student believes that he can speak, listen, understand, and write in English while playing games, he is interested.

We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues in the United States of America and England: - "Creative Problem Solving" to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it ends. the judgment of students is referred to; - as "Merry

Riddles" Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answers to riddles;

- "Quick answers" helps to improve the effectiveness of the lesson;

- "Chigil yozdi" ("Warm-up exercises") use of various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson [3];

- "Pantomime" (pantomime) This method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are performed and students are tired;

- "A chain story" method helps students to develop oral speech; - the "Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. To teach the profession, "They can talk to the interpreters;

- "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, and R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people;

- The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps in teaching English and in developing the oral speech of students, for this, it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;

- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time.

As stated by our first President I. Karimov in his works entitled "High Spirituality-Yengilmaskuch": "If you want to glorify Uzbekistan to the world, glorify its ancient history and bright future, if you want to keep it forever in the memory of generations, first of all, We need to educate young great writers, great poets, and great artists." Therefore, learning a foreign language is a requirement of the current era, and developing new methods of language learning for the young generation based on the "National Personnel Training Program", recommendation for the study process is one of the urgent issues facing scientists and specialists. For our talented young people to become mature specialists in their fields of interest, first of all, they need to have a perfect knowledge of any foreign language, including English.

Therefore, introducing technologies and ensuring that teaching methods meet the requirements of the time are the main tasks of pedagogues-scientists that cannot be delayed. While the economic, political, cultural and educational relations of our country with the countries of the world are growing, the interest of our youth in the life, culture, customs, and language of foreign countries is increasing. In the development of these relations, the role of foreign languages, especially English, is incomparable.

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